

User needs and expectations as a challenging factor for successful living lab research initiatives involving older adults: The DDRI Experience

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Category: Research Paper

Abstract

Despite the number of Living Labs now in existence worldwide and in Europe, there is still a limited amount of academic study and literature to guide their set-up and running. We were particularly interested in ethical guidelines and frameworks to guide research engagement and participation as Coventry University along with partners sought to develop and establish a new LL. This paper therefore intends to shed light on the 'user engagement' aspect, in particular when older adults, and adults with cognitive and physical impairments are involved. To do so, we recruited n=6 residents and n=2 family members from two residential living environments partners of the DDRI programme, a LL pilot initiative led by Coventry University. Methodologically, semi-structured interviews were conducted and the Qualitative Content Analysis (QCA) method used to make sense of the data. A deductive coding frame was built informed by the study goals, and its categories included (among others) 'user engagement', 'user commitment', 'user expectation', 'user needs', 'nature of participation'. The results report on the participant views and concerns about these LL research topics, and provide (ethical) insights for future research collaborations.

Keywords: *User needs, User expectations, Nature of participation, Ethical issues, Living lab, Older adults, Family*

1 Introduction

Living Labs (LLs) are defined as “*user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings*” (ENoLL, 2006). Involvement of users is seen as a “*participative force for co-creating value*”, and facilitating the creation of an innovation *ecosystem* based on a public-private-people partnership in the form of collaborative processes and knowledge sharing (Pallot, Trousse, Senach, & Scapin, 2010, p. 2). This innovation process becomes user-centred (with user as subject) and participatory (with users as partners) increasing user-acceptance of new products, services or processes, and hence reducing the failure rate at the market (Dell'Era & Landoni, 2014; Habibipour, Padyab, Bergvall-Kåreborn, & Ståhlbröst, 2017). Multi-stakeholder collaboration and knowledge sharing is a critical factor to successful LLs (Buitendag, van der Walt, Malebane, & de Jager, 2012; Wenger, McDermott, & Snyder, 2002). For example, Buitendag et al (2012) argue that knowledge creation and knowledge sharing within and outside rural LLs motivate and encourage communication and enhance long-term collaboration between members of different communities of practice. This also supports the idea that multiple perspectives can bring value to each of these partners in an integrative way, and contribute to the LL innovation process and outcome. Ultimately, this becomes a requirement for the success of LLs (Habibipour, Padyab, et al., 2017; Pino et al., 2014; Ståhlbröst, 2012). LLs involve a multi-method approach in which the co-design/co-creation criterion can depend on the degree of involvement and the actual utilization of user feedback and suggestions for the (re-)shaping of the innovation (Schuurman, De Marez, & Ballon, 2015; Schuurman, Mahr, De Marez, & Ballon, 2013); the process of user involvement and participation will also impact the ethical and operational concerns of the LL. However, there is limited academic literature and exploration of how LLs should be developed through stakeholder involvement, to ensure that stakeholder involvement is maintained and optimised. Central to participant and stakeholder involvement is consideration of the key ethical issues as well as how communication is managed through the lifetime of the LL and individual projects within it.

Researchers agree that there is still scarce literature addressing specifically the ethical guidelines involved in the design, development, and implementation of R&D projects (Pino et al., 2014; Sainz, 2012). This is certainly due in part to the nature and characteristics of LLs and the heterogeneity (e.g. in the way the LL concept and approach has been understood and applied) of LL projects shared within the scientific community (Burbridge, 2017; Müller & Sixsmith, 2008; Novitzky et al., 2015; Schuurman et al., 2015; Yazdizadeh & Tavasoli, 2016). The involvement in LLs of older adults, and adults with reducing cognitive and physical capacity poses additional ethical challenges, which include fluctuating capacity or loss of capacity to provide informed consent, participation opt-in and opt-out, involvement of third-parties as

decision makers e.g. children and carers of participants (Novitzky et al., 2015; Panek, Rauhala, & Zagler, 2007; Pino et al., 2014; Sanchez, Taylor, & Bing-Jonsson, 2017). Given this context, this study has been undertaken within the framework of the Data Driven Research and Innovation (DDRI) Programme, a LL initiative which has involved Coventry University and sector partners, and two residential living environments. The first residential environment (later on referred to as ‘Setting A’) offers day care, long-term residential and short-term respite care for older people and people living with dementia or a range of different needs. The second (later on referred to as ‘Setting B’) offers independent living for adults over 55 years, extra care is available for those who need it. The overarching objective of the DDRI Programme is to use data driven analytics and insights to support: independent living; healthy ageing; improved quality of life, well-being and care (self-care or care from others); improved management of particular health conditions; and enabling people to stay in their own homes for longer. A number of DDRI/LL projects have been developed and launched within the two living environments over the last 18 months (see Table 1). One of those projects specifically focused on co-creating with stakeholders’ mechanisms for engaging older adults in individual research studies, with a particular focus on how they are approached to take part, how they are engaged and how they are thanked. The project involved a set of interview studies, followed by co-design workshops to address some of the issues raised.

Table 1. List of some of the DDRI Projects that the participants were briefed on

DDRI Project Title	Objective	Residential Setting
<i>Applied sleep interventions for elderly residents in a care home setting</i>	To explore ways to improve sleep and innovative ways of responding to night-time waking	Setting A
<i>Development of wearable technology to detect dehydration in older adults</i>	To explore the feasibility and design of body worn devices to detect hydration levels and feed-back information to care staff	Setting A & B
<i>Innovation for Dementia Care: Evaluation of Digital Health and Wellbeing Apps in ‘Real-Life’ Living Labs</i>	To explore the potential for digital innovations to improve health and wellbeing for a frail elderly population, including people living with dementia	Setting A & B

<i>The effects of an acoustic monitoring system on night time falls by care home residents with dementia and care staff response</i>	To trial the use of an acoustic monitoring system and assess its effectiveness in preventing night-time falls within a care home for people with dementia	Setting A
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With this study, we aimed to collect the user needs and expectations in relation to participation and engagement in the above LL projects. Participants in this context were the older adults living in the two residential living environments, and their family members. As participation was voluntary, we also investigated the extent to which rewards/incentives could be a possible additional lever for recruitment in research projects.

2 Literature review

In line with this study objective, the literature review here has focussed on the following topics only: i.e. (1) user engagement, motivations and expectations, (2) payment and participation.

User engagement, motivations and expectations are critical inputs to create and sustain a fertile LL context (van Geenhuizen, 2018). User engagement can be driven by a number of activities, which may include promoting clear communication about the project objectives and outcomes, shaping research goals based on user needs and concerns, collaborating with users to help define future research direction, policy or implementation of research outcomes. LLs could experience different degrees of user engagement, running from users as leading co-creators at one extreme to users as passive subjects at the other extreme (i.e. only involved to test/evaluate LL products and/or services) (Almirall, Lee, & Wareham, 2012; van Geenhuizen, 2014). However, engaging users throughout the lifetime of a project is not an easy task, as attention, motivations and expectations tend to decrease over time, and users tend to drop-out from research activities, regardless of the specific phase on the project development process, before they are completed (Habibipour & Bergvall-Kåreborn, 2016; Habibipour, Georges, Schuurman, & Bergvall-Kåreborn, 2017). In particular, user motivation in LL research activities tends to be higher at the beginning, and decreases towards the end of the activities (Habibipour, Padyab, et al., 2017). This trend may be caused by the user's internal factors (intrinsic motivation) or external factors (extrinsic motivation) (Habibipour & Bergvall-Kåreborn, 2016). Researchers now agree that

keeping users motivated and having sustainable user engagement during the whole process of open innovation is of crucial importance. In fact, user drop-out has been acknowledged as having significant (negative) impact on project time and cost efficiency, quality assurance, overall loss of trust and motivation with project participants and stakeholders (Habibipour, Georges, et al., 2017). In their taxonomy for drop-out in LL field tests, Habibipour and Bergvall-Kåreborn (2016) identify three main categories: (1) Innovation-related category, (2) Research-related category and (3) Participant-related category. Within the first category, beside the technological problems (e.g. stability and maturity of prototype), two subcategories involve understanding user needs and participant motivation. The first regards the 'perceived usefulness' of an innovation by the target user; the second 'perceived ease of use', in which complexity in user-interaction, and or readiness of a prototype might affect user motivation. Within the second high-level category (i.e. 'Research-related'), which includes 'Task design', 'Interaction' and 'Timing', in the 'Interaction' subcategory the attention is focused on the level of communication established in the LL between researchers and users and the expectation set. Finally, within 'Participant-related' drop-out are listed the personal issues related to the participant – i.e. the attitude, the context and resources.

LLs, especially with the involvement of older adults, face a range of ethical issues which need to be adequately addressed. The approach to research in this context (especially where academic partners or health or social care partners are involved) will need to undergo a process of formal ethical review and approval. There is clear guidance of research involving older adults and working in high-risk environment, and from specific professional bodies (Bollig, Schmidt, Rosland, & Heller, 2015; BPS, 2009; NSW, 2015; Walsh, 2009). We would argue though that the issues brought together in LLs are complex and multidisciplinary, and navigating the route to clear ethical principles and practice is an ongoing challenge. One of the challenges for example faced in LLs is how to handle an appropriate rewarding and incentive system for users involved in LLs. We are aware of the ethical debate around the use of rewards and incentives to research participation. Here we report what authors in the field have commented in relation to 'rewarding' LL participants for their involvement in LL research activities. For example, Dutilleul et al. (2010) argue that as users in LLs actively involved in co-design and co-creation activities to produce value, there should be rewards in place that secures pay-back to all the actors involved. Incentives may be of different kinds (e.g. vouchers, free tickets, etc.), and can be assigned either at the beginning, after recruitment, or during the trial activities (Georges, Schuurman, & Vervoort, 2016). Others suggest that an inappropriate incentive mechanism, together with issues in building a positive relationship with and mutually between the LL stakeholders, may be among the reasons for participant drop-out (Habibipour, Georges, et al., 2017). Buitendag et al. include this aspect in their definition of LLs, as "*the active participation by the community of practice (CoP) and other stakeholders*

in some or all living lab activities, which may also include in sharing the reward” (Buitendag et al., 2012, p. 221). They argue that ‘rewards’ do not only refer to tangible or financial incentives, but can encompass the underpinning concept of open society for LLs (Buitendag et al., 2012). Along this line, it is argued that LLs support open innovation built “*on voluntary collaboration*” in which each participant has a similar role and relevance (Nyström, Leminen, Westerlund, & Kortelainen, 2014, p. 484; Ståhlbröst & Bergvall-Kåreborn, 2013). Along with Sainz (2012), we suggest that the innovative LL approach would benefit from guidelines and regulations on the ethical aspects inherent to its voluntary and participatory nature, this was the driver for the study described here

3 Methods

The full study was carried out in 2017 over a 12-month period employing a qualitative research approach (Blaikie, 2009; Ritchie, Lewis, Nicholls, & Ormston, 2014). The study received ethical approval from Coventry University Research Ethics Committee. A letter of support was provided by the residential organisations (i.e. Setting A and B). The principles of the British Psychological Society Code of Ethics and Conduct and UK Research Integrity Office’s Code of Practice for Research guided the research.

Participants

Recruitment of residents followed two strategies: in ‘Setting A’ participants were recruited via the recommendation of the staff team, who facilitated the identification of the interested residents; in ‘Setting B’, coffee morning events were organised, and flyers distributed to advertise the research initiative with the proposed projects, and collect resident interests. Overall, n=6 residents agreed to take part in this study, of which n=5 were female (we only recruited residents who were able to provide their informed consent). The average age was M=79.5, where the youngest was 56 years old, and the oldest 90 years old. Two participants currently lived in the care facility (i.e. Setting ‘A’), whilst the other four have been living in independent apartments in Setting B for an average period of 17 months. Further, n=2 family members were recruited. Their parents live in Setting A and at the time of this study were diagnosed with cognitive impairments. For details see Table 2 below.

Table 2. Participants' demographics

#	Role	Male / Female	Setting #	Time at residential setting
RE1	Resident - brain damage age 56, hoping to regain independence.	Female	A	4 months
RE2	Resident, age 90, no dementia	Female	A	12 months
RE3	Resident, age 88	Female	B	16 months
RE4	Resident, age 87	Male	B	10 months
RE5	Resident, age 84	Female	B	18 months
RE6	Resident, age 72	Female	B	24 months
FM1	Family member - mother has dementia, father was also in Setting A	Male	A	12 months
FM2	Family member - father has Parkinson's	Male	A	5 months

Procedure

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with residents and family members. The interview guideline included probing questions to collect opinions (both positive feedback and concerns) about (1) the ongoing DDRI projects in the two living environments (namely in Setting A and Setting B), and (2) ethical issues and concerns. Participants were given short summaries of exemplar DDRI projects by the interviewer of a and questions explored for example their views on each project, concerns about getting involved in it if invited, concerns about giving consent, views on 'thank you's' and the use of incentives for participation. Overall, the average interview length was an hour; resident participants were allowed to take breaks if requested.

The interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim; all transcripts were saved, coded and analysed using NVivo (v.11 Plus for Windows, ©QSR International) (Bazeley, 2007). An NVivo project (entitled 'DDRI-Driven Research and Innovation') was created, which contained all interview transcripts; the selected literature articles; the memo journal keeping track of all activities and decision-making points agreed throughout the development of the research.

Data Analysis

The Qualitative Content Analysis (QCA) method was used to make sense of the data (Schreier, 2012). Critically, the coding frame built to interpret the raw material was informed by the study objectives, and hence followed a concept-driven strategy (Saldana, 2012; Schreier, 2012). In the NVivo project a tree-node structure was created: the parent-nodes (i.e. high-level categories) reflected the relevant themes to the research. A number of child-nodes (i.e. the subcategories) specified each parent node. See below Figure 1 for an overview of the coding frame used.

Name	Sources	References
LL Ethical issues	6	61
Involving Family	5	16
Opt-out	5	10
Paperwork and consent	5	19
Rewarding	6	16
LL_DDRI projects	8	144
Engaging with older adults (C	7	22
Expectations set	6	26
General views on LL projects	8	33
Involvement in research	8	35
Perceived needs	6	21
User motivation	3	7

Figure 1. Concept-driven coding frame used to categorise the study data (from the NVivo project)

All interviews were coded using the proposed coding frame. The segmentation strategy used as coding unit was the 'meaning unit' (that is, any portion of text, regardless of length, to which it was believed a code may apply) (Coffey & Atkinson, 1996; Grbich, 2013; Saldana, 2012).

4 Findings

Involving older adults, and adults with physical (e.g. sight or hearing impairments) or mental (e.g. dementia) disorders poses additional challenges for the researcher. Some of these challenges include the design of an inclusive consent form and participant information; the involvement of family, or others to provide consent should capacity to consent be diminished. Mechanisms for sharing information and gaining consent were discussed. Information about the DDRI projects was circulated in the two residential settings by means of Project Information Sheets (PIS). Colour images and short paragraphs of text (using Arial 14 font) were used to describe the different

active projects, and assess the resident interest before asking them to sign the informed consent. Overall, this approach was commented positively. Further, participants highlighted the need to consider individual needs:

“Sight and hearing are important. We all look normal enough but everyone’s got some kind of underlying problem. For the people who are partly blind or blind, it could be read out to them. You would have here a few with sight problems”.

The involvement of third parties in the process of consent to participate in a study was also discussed. Involving the family, or a ‘carer network’ is well accepted by all residents, as they are conscious of their deteriorating physical and mental conditions, but recognised participant wishes and attitudes should still very much be considered. This also may include the possibility to withdraw from the LL research initiative due to health factors.

“Well I mean if you as the researcher thinks that the person is no longer quite capable of doing it, then I think that’s reasonable [to involve the family]”.

“Family or carers then need to know what the person concerned attitude was in relation to research”.

Challenges around the location of family members were raised and how this might affect recruitment to studies if they were not easy to get hold of and consult:

“I don’t know my family is fairly well scattered around the country, there’s none of them that are local. But they are already aware of different aspect concerning my health, so this involves not only this project”.

All of the presented DDRI projects (see Table 1) were found to be of interest to the participants’ and indeed the feedback was positive. Reactions like ‘*This sounds interesting*’, ‘*Well, I think that’s a brilliant idea*’, ‘*I’d very much welcome something like that*’ were collected. The project related to sleep interventions raised particular interest among the residents in both settings, as it was commented that sleep is an issue at their age. Hence, a number of questions in relation to potential side effects, dosage, and food sensitivities were asked. The project about hydration level detection also raised attention and the resident comments – particularly in relation to wearing the proposed technology – were positive. Overall, the discussion about the LL projects

showed how the residents (in particular in Setting 'B') can discern their needs and what could be good (or not) for their health.

"This is another one that's right in my area of concern. I can't get to sleep at night without an intake of zopiclones, [...]. I notice that in your project you've got separate ideas, like the milky drink – but I'm sensitive to milk and any dairy, cheese or anything of that sort so that rules that out for me but I get the tryptophan from bananas and dates, dried dates. You know, I got a lot of faith in a nutrition book that I've got down here".

"I recognise the importance of hydration and my general health dictates that I do have a good intake of, water on one hand but then again I have prostrate problems so that is quite a problem for me getting it right...but a research into it is wonderful".

It was interesting to gain a sense of user motivation to take part in research. The older adult residents, identified being motivated to be engaged in something challenging that could help maintain their mental capabilities:

"I like to get involved with these sorts of things because I think it keeps my brain working. To be honest with you, it's just like if you just sat here in this flat and did nothing. I couldn't do that I have got to be doing something, and I say it I don't mean physically, I mean mentally!".

The intrinsic motivation linked to specific recognition that participation in studies might support their own health and satisfy their interests. Their perception of the value of the study and participation encouraged influenced overall resident attitude in relation to research participation. Residents commented that supporting research and the 'general good' are important aspects to them, either because they believe in what the research is aiming to, or given their personal and educational background.

"Well if they were told by doing research that they were likely to get better, have better sleep they would, should be taking part. And even if they didn't I mean it would help somebody somewhere".

"See, when you came we didn't really know what we were taking part in, we didn't really understand what it was but it's really future research that will help people in the future more than us probably".

"But then it depends on the background of the person, you know they wouldn't normally, well they've just never heard of it. I think that's for your educational background and what sort of research"

Many factors can affect the residents' attitudes towards research participation, both positively and negatively. These may include culture (e.g. what it means to get engaged in research), period of life (e.g. living in senior living settings), personal beliefs, etc. For example, in more than one interview it was highlighted that the word 'research' seems to convey a negative connotation, and consequently led to a feeling of distance from the issue and closure.

"I can only tell you the impression I get from talking with people here. I feel that quite a lot of people, they are not really interested. They got to the stage in life where they just really don't want to be bothered".

"I feel that as soon as you say research they'll say "Oh no-- I'm not interested, thank you. I think so because they think of researchers are really going inside you".

"I don't tend to do surveys at all, particularly on the phone. They ring you up and say we're just doing a survey. I just say --no. I don't do surveys on the phone and put the phone down!".

"Getting involved with things like these I wouldn't do it, not knowing your background, knowing where you came from sort of thing I mean I wouldn't do it to anybody who just came to the door and asked me to do it".

Further, the interviews highlighted that those wanting to involve older adults in research should also consider how older people can personally manage being part of a LL research initiative and how researchers should take their needs into account in study design and delivery, particularly with pace of all procedures involved, etc. One resident commented about some possible unexpected reactions, pointing at the potential vulnerability and variation in capabilities of older people.

"You see, there are people with slight irritable problems, get het up very quickly, the sight of a piece of paper that they have to listen to and do anything with it is beyond them. Apart from that, don't put any pressure on them. You know, it's how much they can cope with and you don't know whether it's because of their underlying illness or not, you just accept them as they are and then just work around them. [...] You know, refer back to what you did and if somebody has a better feeling than they might do anyway".

The participants had clear views on the benefits to them of participating. They would like acknowledgement and to know about the impact of the input they made or the valuable future impact in society. This also included their attitudes toward research participation. Although during the recruitment process it was suggested to consider

rewards as a motivation factor for participating, all participants were volunteers. When prompted about the topic, both residents and family members confirmed that participation should happen without the need of rewards.

"We should all do our bit and not expect a reward".

"I think if you're interested, you do it, just do it. I mean I can't see why we need to have a reward".

"No. No rewards. That drives the wrong behaviour doesn't it?"

They do not necessarily expect a 'personal' thank you, but they expected to receive information about the outcomes the project had achieved, any next step, etc. The same view was shared by the family members

"You know having participated in that little bit of research, it obviously links into something else and it could be nice if you can hear about it and think: "well I feel quite proud of that because I helped".

"It would be nice to get the outcome be it in the form of an e-mail, a general e-mail to everyone and what the contribution was and how it's resulted".

In line with the above, the interviewed family members were very aware of their parent's health condition, and what this entails in terms of communication and interaction (e.g. the need to repeat a number of times the research questions - posed in a Yes/No way - to get the answer), and how both physical and mental conditions may deteriorate as the research proceeds.

"I don't think this would be a concern, it would be good because I know how Mum communicates [...] by her pointing, so even without saying anything that's communicating. [...] The only thing that I think that would be difficult is if you were to spend an extended period of time with her to get her to do one single thing because of her concentration levels, she'd get tired very quickly. So, it should be a gently, gently approach really".

"That's part of the thing -- if this is no longer suitable for my Dad's condition or somebody else's condition, we just need to step outside the trial please".

5 Conclusions

This study was part of a bigger research initiative carried out within the DDRI Programme that involved a number of LL studies carried out in two residential living environments with older adults, and adults with physical and cognitive impairments. A qualitative research strategy was used, and interviews conducted with the research participants to explore user needs and expectations in engaging in LL research initiatives, and ethical issues connected to this.

Overall, LL research initiatives leveraging greater interest among older people address health topics close to the current user needs (e.g. sleeping issues, body hydration, etc.). This can have an impact on the residents' intrinsic motivation towards research participation. Other factors may drive the overall motivation, such as cultural aspects, which resulted in several valuable feedback responses. One concern was related to the connotation that the word 'research' may convey to older people, and possible alternative 'labels' to define LL 'research' initiatives have been advanced, including "Adult caring research" or "We want your views". Further, as LL projects involve medium-, long-term collaborations with research participants, it is argued that it is vital to maintain the ongoing interest and cooperation, as well as expectations, of research participants, family and other stakeholders for successful research initiatives.

More light has also been shed in relation to critical ethical concerns when LL initiatives engage with older adults, and adults with physical and mental impairments. This included the nature of participation in LL research initiatives (i.e. voluntarily. rewarded), opting out from research, or involving family in the decision-making process when the physical and mental condition of elderly persons may put their participation at risk. The findings informed subsequent co-design sessions to develop acceptable briefing information and research processes for gaining consent and meaningful participation within the DDRI model that are reported elsewhere.

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